

Solar Energy Optimization Via a Remote Research Platform

Data Management Plan (DMP)

1 Collecte des données et documentation

1.1 Quelles données allez-vous collecter, étudier, générer ou réutiliser ?

Within the frame of the present project, a large variety of simulated and experimental data will be generated. As they can be of interest for other researchers or institutions, efforts will be made to collect them according to the existing procedures, to store them on secure supports, servers and repositories and finally to make them available to the interested people and scientific communities.

Based on the work packages of the project, simulated and experimental data will be collected. They are related to the mechanical design of the solar energy systems (PV panels, CPV modules, CPV-T modules, STC modules), the settings of the parameters, the operational conditions, the solar system models and their different control algorithms for sun tracking as well as the follow-up of the measurements during the tests and experimentation phase. The experimentation phase will be conducted under different weather conditions in 3 locations: HES-SO Valais in Sion/Switzerland, University of Amirkabir in Tehran/Iran and University of Kurdistan in Sanandaj/Iran.

The solar systems are equipped with appropriate sensors to measure different important variables such as voltage, current, electrical energy and power, thermal energy and losses, temperature, solar radiation, energy efficiency and so on.

Depending on the research questions, we will need to collect quantitative and qualitative data:

- The quantitative datasets are available in multiple file formats (Rdata, xlsx, csv, txt, tab, mat,...) compatible with most common software packages. The form of these datasets will be tables containing time-based measurements of each of the variables and different settings for the specific overarching conditions.
- They qualitative datasets will be complemented by a set of data interpretations, observations and analysis made by the operators and researchers and recorded in electronic lab notebooks or MS Word reports. In addition, Matlab Static tools and the statistics package "R" will be used to perform data analysis.

The number of datasets generated will depend on the variety of the system parameters tested and the number of tests conducted during the project on the 3 sites (Sion, Tehran, Sanadaj), under different weather conditions within 3 years.

All the data stored can be re-used indirectly in the form of gained know-how and for side-by side comparison, efficiency evaluation and optimization of the solar systems and improving the sun tracking of one-axis and two-axis solar energy systems.

1.2 Comment les données seront-elles recueillies, étudiées ou générées ?

Current State research and cutting-edge technologies and methodologies will be

employed to generate, collect and analyse data. Standard research procedures will be followed, using high quality sensors, materials and equipment to assure the quality of the data.

The reliability of the results is expressed by different methods:

- Modeling the solar devices by using meteorological data and applying experimental identification approaches
- Manipulating the parameters and operational conditions and measuring their efficiency effects experimentally
- Comparing the energy gain of the sun tracker modules with the fixed solar devices
- Comparing the energy gain obtained by the sun tracker modules in the 3 sites (Sion, Sanandaj, Tehran)
- Reiterating the same experimentation in identical conditions
- Comparing the measurements with existing results from other research organisations, scientific publications, depositories, etc.
- Validating the results with the numerical simulations and the hard-ware-in-loop simulations
- Analyzing the consistency and the differences between the existing results, the simulated results, the anticipated results and the actual experimental results

For every experimentation, data will be organized in folders named by the date and time. They will contain the dataset composed of all raw data collected in an electronic file (MS Excel or more sophisticated tools) and a report containing more elaborated data (MS Word or more elaborated format). A template for the MS Excel and MS Word files will be established at the beginning of the project to maintain a homogeneous format along the project.

File Naming is often taken for granted. Best practice is the descriptive names to reflect the content of the file. Some suggested attributes to include:

- unique identifier or project name/acronym
- PI
- location/spatial coordinates
- year of study
- data type
- version number
- file type

And finally version Control is the way to track revisions of a data set, or a process. As our research project involves more than one person, it is essential. We will keep track of the changes to a file in the file naming convention and log files, or version control software. File sharing software can also be used to track versions.

1.3 Quelle documentation et quelles métadonnées allez-vous fournir avec les données ?

Metadata in our project has the following objectives:

- To provide information about all the data generated in the project
- To help users to find the relevant information and discover the different resources
- To organize, archive and preserve electronic resources

In the metadata files, the following information will be provided, according to a common pre-established template:

- 1) Time and date of collection, geographic location, author and his/her contributing to the data collection
- 2) The objective of the measurement
- 3) The principle of the measurement, when extraordinary and relevant
- 4) Procedure for the preparation of the measurements, when relevant
- 5) Procedure, methodology and structure used for experimentation
- 6) Any relevant experimental conditions and temporal characteristics for the raw data files
- 7) Specifications regarding the variables provided in the measurement file (units, significance, accuracy)

In some cases, data acquisition software automatically includes part of the metadata in the raw data files and sometimes it also allows the addition of supplementary remarks, which can cover the points in the above list.

2 Questions éthiques, légales et de sécurité

2.1 Comment les questions éthiques seront-elles abordées et traitées ?

To our knowledge, no unpublished data from external sources will be exploited in the present project. Preliminary data and current know-how will however be required for the success of the project, but it is not protected by any confidentiality agreement.

A common server will be created for facilitating the sharing of the information between the partners. It will contain three subfolders, one for each of the partners and some additional common subfolders for the collection of administrative and management documents of the consortium, common literature sources, reporting activities and dissemination of the results (publications, conference presentations, etc.).

Each of the research partner has the right to possess and store the datasets and the metadata that are generated within his/her own research group and to decide when to share it with the other partners. However, the sharing of the data and results within the consortium will be promoted by a formal and binding non-disclosure agreement/confidentiality contract, setting the exact terms for the dissemination of results generated within the consortium. Basically, it will be set that no shared data, results and information are disclosed to any third-party entity before the permission by the partner owning the dataset or by the other partners of the consortium. The permission will be formally asked and provided, by written (a common email is considered sufficient). This will occur especially, but not only, before submitting any abstract to a conference or paper to a journal. In these cases, the content of the article, abstract, poster, presentation is communicated to the other partners for proofreading. This agreement can hold at least for 5 years after the end of the project.

The use of data which have been published by another partner follows the standard rules of copyright. It will be the decision of each research group leader to select who, in his/her group, has access to the data generated in his/her own group. The data shared within the consortium (common folder) will be shared in each research group only with the collaborator, which is directly involved in the present project, and in agreement with the other project partners.

In case the data generated are made accessible to third-party entities, the metadata should be modified in order to remove the name of the person which have been performing the measurements and the selection of the information shared should be made in full agreement between the partners. The same procedure applies for any data made public, for instance in publication or as supplementary information of a publication.

This project does not involve personal or sensitive data management and therefore is not implying any ethical issue regarding the management of this specific kind of data.

2.2 Comment seront gérés l'accès aux données et la sécurité ?

Management, regulation, access and permission procedures regarding the datasets generated within the frame of this project by any of the partners of the consortium was specified in the previous section. Only authorized personnel have access to the server and the common folders. The access will be restricted by a password.

As the present project does not involve any personal or sensitive data storage, no additional stronger data security procedure needs to be implemented.

Ownership of datasets and dissemination of datasets and secondary results, as well as any other kinds of IPs will be specified in an IPR ownership agreement, which will be set in a collaboration between IP offices of the 3 institutions involved. Within this document, it shall be mentioned that should an invention be patented, the license will follow the IP rules of the institution hosting the group in which data were generated.

3 Stockage et préservation des données

3.1 De quelle manière vos données seront-elles stockées et sauvegardées au cours de la recherche ?

Regardless of how much data research will be generated, we need a storage procedure which will meet the needs of the project. While USB drives, hard drives, and disks are cheap and easy solutions, they are not secure and can be easily lost or destroyed. That is why we propose to use multiple methods to backup and copy research data:

- Local storage solutions such as lab/project server, CD, USB drives, portable hard drives, etc.
- Secured cloud services
- Centrally managed secured servers

The secured servers provided by the institutions will be preferentially employed. They usually provide large volumes of storage, which are expected to be sufficient for the present project.

We will use an automatic backup process for the transfer and back up of the data, on a regular basis. Typically, the administrator configures the systems/network that need to be backed up. Once configured, the data, research results and applications from the selected device are automatically copied, transferred over the network and stored on the backup server. The administrator just needs to specify the type and time of the automatic backup within the backup software.

All the raw and treated data will be conserved on the servers for the whole length of the project and for at least 5 years after the end of the project.

As storing data on a hard drive or a server is neither "data archiving" nor "data preservation, we will use Zenodo as the project repository. Thereby, the short-term and long-term storage of the research data will be secured since all the data are stored safely in the same cloud infrastructure as research data from CERN.

3.2 Quel est votre plan en matière de conservation des données ?

As mentioned above, a common folder will be created, in which all relevant data to be shared between the partners will be saved. This common folder will be probably saved on a secured server of HES-SO (to be decided) and be protected by a password. It will be kept for at least 5 years after the end of the project. It aims at the preservation of datasets and secondary data that can be of any future use for any of the partners, but also for third-party, if required. The selection of the data will be made based on the quality of the datasets, but not on the result itself, for example bad and irregular results will also be stored. The selection of the data preserved over time will be the responsibility of each research group leader, in discussion with the researchers involved.

Preserving research data is more complex than just saving it on a hard drive or server. It is rarely feasible to preserve all data generated during a research project. For data preservation, we will focus on data that is unique or difficult to replicate. The most responsible way to preserve the research data is to

use a data repository such as Zenodo.

Zenodo uses digital preservation strategies to store multiple online replicas and to back up the files (Data files and metadata). In addition, it provides data curation services (data integrity checks, format migrations and the creation of descriptive records) as well as sharing and publication of data and research results.

In Zenodo, all formats are allowed - even preservation unfriendly. Total files size limit per record is 50GB. Higher quotas can be requested and granted on a case-by-case basis. For Zenodo general policies, see <https://about.zenodo.org/policies/>

4 Partage et réutilisation des données

4.1 De quelle manière et où seront partagées les données ?

Data with a potential interest for third-party will be deposited in a repository, on a regular basis for example every 6 months, upon agreement between the partners of the consortium. The repository Zenodo proposes an easy-to-use and innovative service that enables researchers and research institutions to share and showcase multidisciplinary research results (data and publications). Furthermore, Zenodo assigns a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) to all publicly available uploads, in order to make content easily and uniquely citable. Therefore, this repository fulfills the main requirements imposed for data sharing, archiving, promoting and preservation of the data generated in our project.

In all the publications, links towards this repository will be established, as well as on the various academic online profiles of the group leaders and of the involved collaborators, such as LinkedIn, ResearchGate, etc.

If more specific repositories appear during the project, the partners may decide to use other digital repositories (Dryad, EUDAT) with FAIR data principles and maintained by a non-profit organisation, to increase the visibility of their datasets and research results.

4.2 Y a-t-il des restrictions nécessaires pour protéger les données sensibles ?

Data will mostly be released together with a publication in a scientific journal. Sets of data not entering this scope will be released at the latest 5 years after the end date of the project or before, in agreement with all partners of the consortium.

The only limitation to make publicly available data generated within the consortium is to obtain a full agreement from the research partners. One of the research partners can limit the publication of data of the consortium if this is data generated within his/her own research group and he is planning a future publication or release of the data.

4.3 Je confirme que je choisirai exclusivement des bases de données (repositories) numériques conformes aux FAIR Data Principles

Oui

4.4 Les bases de données (repositories) choisies pour le dépôt des données sont gérées par une organisation à but non lucratif.

Oui